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Boosting Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy in water biomonitoring - BIOLAWEB

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Project "Boosting Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy in Water Biomonitoring" (BIOLAWEB) aims to strengthen the research and innovation capacity of the Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade (UB-ICTM) in biodiversity assessment and biomonitoring. UB-ICTM researchers made a noticeable contribution to the study of biodiversity, community ecology, and conservation of water bodies in South-Eastern Europe. However, a knowledge on index development and intercalibration following the EU standards for lakes and watercourse monitoring is still lacking in this geographic region. Similarly, there is a knowledge gap in DNA-based ecological status assessment in SEE. Overcoming these gaps and achieving the objectives of the BIOLAWEB is realized through networking with international institutions with a strong expertise in metabarcoding approach and in biological indices development: the French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE) and the Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA). Staff exchange, common field, and laboratory work, and a variety of courses are used for an effective knowledge transfer from the partnering institutions to UB-ICTM. In order to strengthen research and innovation capacity, through BIOLAWEB project the International Cooperation and Project Office was established at UB-ICTM to support project application, management, and reporting at the international level.

The implementation of the BIOLAWEB results will raise the research profile of the coordinator and partner institutions and contribute to UB-ICTM's vision of becoming a lighthouse for attracting the best talents and tackling the burning issues of environmental assessment.

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